

Strengthening Wildfire Resilience: International Practices

Dear colleague,

We warmly invite you to contribute to an **international study on wildfire resilience, gathering place-based insights into the opportunities and challenges of building resilience across fire-prone regions worldwide**. By drawing on your knowledge and experience of specific regions, systems dynamics, communities, or projects, your participation will:

- facilitate global knowledge exchange by contributing to an open-source database of resilience-oriented approaches across wildfire governance domains, available to both practitioners and academics;
- help develop a global blueprint for adaptive, contextually grounded wildfire resilience strategies;
- inform real-world design and planning, including the rebuilding of a recently fire-affected wildland–urban landscape; and
- contribute to a broader analysis of how ‘good’ and ‘bad’ fire are understood and mobilised in policy and practice.

Building on these insights, we will publish an original research article comparing resilience across international case-studies, and edit a peer-reviewed scientific volume on wildfire resilience strategies to maximise accessibility and foster global action, with invited chapters authored by survey participants. See *‘Acknowledgement and Collaboration’* below for acknowledgement options and collaboration opportunities.

This study is led by Princeton University with collaborators from Imperial College London, King’s College London, MIT, Caltech, the Technical University of Crete, California State University Long Beach, and global partners including fire management agencies, practitioners, and community leaders. We welcome contributions from experts (academic and practitioner) focusing on:

- specific aspects of resilience (e.g., governance, policy, fuel management, insurance, urban design, infrastructure), or
- multiple dimensions of resilience within a single case study area.

Amid rapidly intensifying, multi-systemic wildfire risk, your perspective is especially valuable now. The survey is open from **mid-September to 23rd November** and takes **10–30 minutes** depending on the detail you provide. If short on time, you may focus on **Section 2** (placed-based examples of opportunities and challenges), using brief notes or citing literature. All levels of input are valuable, and we encourage you to share the survey with colleagues, collaborators, and fire-user networks to ensure diverse representation and strengthen global knowledge exchange.

We are deeply grateful for your contribution to this collective effort. The sections below provide further details on the study’s motivation, survey structure, data security, and collaboration opportunities. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to get in touch, we would be delighted to continue the conversation.

Respectfully,

I | Background Information and Research Imperative

'Wildfire resilience' is widely invoked in policy and practice, referring to the capacity of systems to withstand, adapt to, and recover from extreme or novel fire events while sustaining ecological integrity and social values. It spans three interconnected dimensions:

- basic resilience - absorbing and recovering from disturbance,
- adaptive resilience - adjusting internal dynamics in response to change, and
- transformative resilience – restructuring systems or goals to reduce vulnerability and enhance functionality.

Despite its ubiquity, the concept demands critical engagement. Key challenges include rigid yet inconsistent terminology and methods for classifying fire; tensions over fire's dual role as both destructive and regenerative in fire-adapted, fire-tolerant, and fire-dependent ecosystems; and the institutionalisation of 'good fire' through prescribed early dry season burning regimes, positioned as a corrective to colonially inherited fire suppression policies.

Wildfire is increasingly recognised as a meta-coupled social–ecological phenomenon, shaped by interactions among biophysical, topographic, and sociocultural factors. Risk and resilience are mediated not only by climate but also by non-climate strategies, particularly the intentional use of fire to reduce extreme events and sustain ecosystem functioning.

Unlike many natural hazards that fall within narrow governance domains (e.g., regulation of earthquakes, financial mechanisms for floods), wildfire governance is fragmented across multiple institutional and discursive arenas. These shape whether fire is framed as disaster, ecological process, or cultural practice, and together determine the '*action situation*' where information is shared, management options are negotiated, and interventions are implemented and evaluated. Such governance complexity makes resilience strategies highly sensitive to shifting risk perceptions, political pressure, questions of legitimacy and liability, and market forces, often stalling decision-making and complicating cross-context assessment.

Achieving wildfire resilience thus requires engaging with risk, ecology, meaning, and memory across institutional and epistemological traditions, particularly under climate change and increasingly non-linear socioecological dynamics.

II | Survey Information and Invitation

While there is not, and should not be, a single strategy for achieving wildfire resilience across diverse pyro-geographies, valuable lessons can be drawn from international practices to strengthen resilience in fire-prone regions worldwide. This survey seeks place-based insights into how resilience is understood, enacted, and constrained in specific contexts. Therefore, we invite you to draw on your knowledge and experience in fire-prone areas to help identify what has worked, what has not, and the enabling conditions, barriers, and temporal dynamics (e.g., political cycles, geopolitical relations, climate shocks, market volatility) shaping resilience-oriented decisions, as well as to highlight critical research and policy gaps. Where contextually appropriate, these grounded perspectives may inform mitigation and adaptation interventions in other fire-prone areas that respect historical fire regimes and sociocultural specificities, learning from international "best" practices.

Here, *'fire-prone'* refers broadly to systems where fire is ecologically beneficial (e.g., fire-adapted, fire-dependent, fire-tolerant), as well as those where it is primarily destructive (e.g., fire-sensitive, fire-novel, fire-resistant).

Framework

The survey is guided by a novel Social-Ecological Systems–Pyrogeographic Framework integrating six wildfire governance domains:

- regulatory,
- financial (market-based),
- infrastructural/technocratic,
- community-based (social),
- humanitarian (disaster-oriented), and
- ecological,

within a broader discursive-ideological landscape (see Fig. 1; Table 1).

This framework conceptualises wildfire as a meta-coupled phenomenon, with many management strategies spanning frequently siloed governance domains. By mapping their interactions and applying pyrogeographic thinking to decision-making, it clarifies how governance arrangements arise in specific social-ecological contexts and shape fire's understanding, management, and lived experience. Distilling these dynamics into a single adaptive structure provides a practical tool for addressing wildfire's 'wicked' risks, characterised by contested definitions, feedbacks, and powerful political, economic, and sociocultural forces.

Survey Instructions

This survey has four sections:

1. Defining wildfire resilience
2. Identifying opportunities and challenges for resilience using a Social-Ecological Systems–Pyrogeographic Framework
3. Highlighting critical research gaps
4. (*Optional*) Reflecting on perceptions of 'good' and 'bad' fire

Section 1 asks you to define wildfire resilience, with reference to extreme wildfires that exceed historical variability. We also recognise that ecologically beneficial fire is integral to resilience in many systems; please include these dimensions where relevant.

Section 2 asks you to identify opportunities and challenges for resilience in your context(s), providing place-based detail wherever possible. If you work across multiple geographies or broader scales, please anchor responses in identifiable locations. This section is structured on our Social-Ecological Systems–Pyrogeographic Framework, therefore please situate your examples within one of six wildfire governance domains, or within the seventh category, *'ideological landscape'* (e.g., risk perception, public understanding, social narratives). Domains often overlap, but please place each example in the domain you consider most determinative. Feel free skip questions related to governance domains outside your expertise, as well as share supplementary information, examples, or links to relevant sources, especially for aspects not explicitly covered in the survey.

We welcome both targeted interventions (e.g., related to risk assessment, hazard prevention, suppression, emergency response, and recovery planning) and indirect interventions (e.g., related to ecosystem management and governance arrangements shaping fire regimes). Reflection on broader systemic dynamics (e.g., political, economic, climatic) is strongly encouraged. Before completing this section, please review the framework (Fig. 1) and example strategies (Table 1). Feedback on the framework itself, including suggested revisions or additions, is also welcome.

Section 3 asks you to highlight critical research gaps that, if addressed, could advance wildfire resilience globally or within specific contexts. You may wish to draw on wider disciplinary perspectives, theories, or frameworks.

Section 4 (optional) invites reflection on how ‘good’ and ‘bad’ fire are conceptualised in your work or research, how this framing is mobilised, and its implications for management.

Acknowledgement and Collaboration

Please provide your full name, email address, institutional or organisational affiliation, and job title/role if you indicate any (≥ 1) of the following preferences:

1. You would like to be acknowledged in any publications resulting from this work.
2. You are interested in contributing to the development of an original research article comparing global case studies (note: all named participants will be acknowledged; please only select this option if you would like to hear more about potential co-authorship, subject to contribution in line with journal authorship guidelines).
3. You are interested in collaborating with other survey participants to work on a research project addressing gaps identified in Section 3.
4. You are interested in hearing more about the planned scientific volume on international wildfire resilience practice and would like to be considered for potential chapter authorship.
5. Other – please specify

If you express interest in any of the above, Abigail Croker will be in contact once the survey period concludes in November. If you choose not to provide your name or email address, or do not select any options, your responses will remain anonymous, and there will be no further contact regarding this work.

Data Privacy and Security

This study has been reviewed and approved by the Princeton University Institutional Review Board (IRB): **Princeton University IRB Project #18440**.

This survey is hosted on Princeton University’s secure Qualtrics platform. Data are stored on encrypted servers in line with Princeton’s information security and privacy policies. All responses are confidential and used only for the purposes outlined. Personally identifying information will be collected only if you voluntarily provide it at the end of the survey; it will be securely stored and accessible only to the core research team.

Note: If you select options 3 and/or 4, you may be included in group email threads with other survey participants who expressed similar interests. If you prefer not to be included, please avoid these options or contact Abigail directly for alternative arrangements. See [Princeton University’s Privacy Policy](#) for further details.

Figure 1. Adapted joint Social-Ecological Systems–Pyrogeographic (SESP) Framework for understanding wildfire risk and resilience.

(a) Social-ecological systems (SES) framework adapted from McGinnis & Ostrom (2014), Marshall (2015), and Vogt et al. (2015), extended to include Ecological Rules (ER), Transformation Systems (TS), and Products (P).

(b) Wildfire governance system presented as an enlarged view of the Governance System (GS). Wildfire governance is depicted as a multi-layered yet fragmented structure spanning regulatory, infrastructural, financial, community-based, humanitarian, and ecological domains that arise in specific social-ecological contexts and are embedded within a broader discursive–ideological environment that frames, contests, and legitimises fire.

(c) Pyrogeographic framing of the Focal Action Situation, showing fire’s interdependence with climate and biology, topography, and society and culture. The coincidence of spatiotemporally variable atmospheric conditions, consumable resources, and ignition agents produces diverse fire regimes. While governance does not independently determine this landscape, it shapes how it is conceptualised, narrated, and managed.

Together, these perspectives converge in the action situation, the arena where information about the pyrogeographic landscape is shared, processed, and debated (a, I), and where management options are negotiated and implemented, shaping outcomes (a, O). Outcomes are contingent on competing institutional, market, and sociocultural narratives of fire that influence risk perception, public understanding, policy legitimacy, liability, and the feasibility of resilience strategies. These dynamics underscore how wildfire resilience is shaped by cross-domain governance complexity and vulnerability to shifting political, social, and market pressures.

Table 1. Wildfire governance system depicted as a multi-layered yet fragmented structure spanning regulatory, financial (market-based), infrastructural/technocratic, community-based (social, both formal and informal), humanitarian (disaster-oriented), and ecological domains, embedded within a broader discursive–ideological environment that frames, contests, and legitimises fire (Figure 1, a, b). These domains collectively shape the Focal Action Situation, determining how fire is conceptualised, narrated, and managed (Figure 1, c).

Each domain is defined based on the mechanisms applied to govern wildfires, along with examples of associated management strategies. Many wildfire challenges (e.g., air pollution and human health) and strategies span multiple, overlapping domains, hence should be understood as interconnected components of a broader governance system, not as discrete, isolated categories. All domains operate within a wider discursive ideological landscape.

Discursive ideological landscape: broad definition

The discursive ideological landscape shapes how wildfires, risks, and management strategies are understood, legitimised, and implemented. Competing narratives, norms, and framings of fire (as disaster, ecological process, or sociocultural practice) circulate through media, political debate, public discourse, and scientific communication, influencing public perception, political priorities, and policy conditions. This domain reflects evolving narratives around climate change, biodiversity loss, and rural marginalisation, as well as cultural and economic losses, pollution, liability, and acceptable risk thresholds. It also encompasses contestations over ‘good’ versus ‘bad’ fire, Indigenous fire stewardship and cultural burning, and suppression orthodoxy versus ecological fire use. These framings directly influence risk perception, political acceptability, and public support, shaping the viability of interventions across all wildfire governance domains.

Governance domain	Broad definition	Examples of wildfire management strategies
Regulatory	The use of formal rules (laws, policies, codes, and standards) established by mandated authorities to guide wildfire preparedness, response, and recovery. Regulatory mechanisms assign responsibilities, establish compliance requirements, and define penalties for non-compliance.	Operational suppression and firefighting deployment; occupational health and safety; Incident Command systems; ignition control (e.g., liability, negligence, equipment standards); land-use planning (zoning, permitting, sprawl control); structural and property-level fuel management (defensible space, building codes, home hardening); community and wildland fuel management (burn permits, prescribed fires, thinning); air quality regulations; public health code; fire danger restrictions; hazardous materials control; utility regulations (e.g., mandated power shutoffs); liability frameworks and condemnation procedures (e.g., inverse condemnation); emergency declarations (e.g., evacuation orders, curfews).
Financial (market-based)	The use of market-based tools, such as incentives (subsidies, grants, insurance) and disincentives (penalties, taxes), to influence wildfire risk management, resource distribution, and cost-sharing. Financial mechanisms can motivate risk reduction, support resilience investments, and facilitate risk transfer (e.g., insurance), often delegating responsibility to private actors under public oversight.	Insurance schemes (including parametric insurance, cross-subsidisation, liability-driven investment); utility rate structures (distributing wildfire mitigation costs across customers); catastrophe bonds (CAT bonds); risk-pooling and catastrophe funds (e.g., reinsurance markets, regional insurance pools, mutual-aid agreements); public subsidies and grants for risk reduction (e.g., defensible space, fuel management, community resilience); cost-sharing programmes; performance

(results)-based incentives (e.g., Payment for Ecosystem Services schemes); market penalties for failing to implement required risk reduction.

Infrastructural/technocratic	The use of engineered systems, technical planning, and advanced technologies to guide wildfire prevention, mitigation, and response, and enhance public safety, informed by real-time and historical fire behaviour. This domain emphasises data-driven decision-making, hazard modelling, situational awareness, and infrastructure resilience, prioritising efficiency, predictive control, and standardised evaluation of management effectiveness.	Detection, surveillance, and real-time monitoring (e.g., remote sensing, satellite imagery, sensor networks, drones); predictive modelling and AI-driven risk forecasting; hazard ratings and risk metrics (e.g., fire weather indices, exposure models); early-warning systems; technical mapping of population, asset, and infrastructure exposure; air quality and smoke detection systems; clean air transport corridors; integrated data platforms for operational coordination; automated detection and suppression systems (e.g., critical infrastructure); firefighting infrastructure (e.g., access roads, water storage); firefighting resources (personnel, vehicles, aerial suppression); infrastructure resilience (e.g., fire-adapted infrastructure, fire breaks, utility protection); expert advisory panels.
Community-based (social)	<p>Formal: structured mechanisms enabling community participation within official wildfire management systems, recognised by or integrated with state, agency, or organisational frameworks. Often linked to formal roles, legal instruments, and institutional processes, with conditional access to resources.</p> <hr/> <p>Informal/customary: locally rooted, unofficial, or traditional practices that guide decision-making, knowledge-sharing, and fire stewardship, fostering shared responsibility outside formal governance structures. This domain reflects adaptive, place-based knowledge systems, social networks, and intergenerational practices, though participation and equitable outcomes may be constrained by structural vulnerabilities, including socioeconomic barriers or limited access to technology.</p>	<p>Community fire brigades, volunteer firefighting units, and local roles in incident management; community-led prescribed burns under agency oversight (e.g., Prescribed Burn Associations, emissions abatement schemes); Indigenous Fire Stewardship within regulatory fire management systems via permits, agreements, or funding; preparedness programmes with certification and conditional funding (e.g., Firewise, FireSmart); formal community wildfire planning instruments (e.g., Community Wildfire Protection Plans); agency-led engagement and education; social equity and vulnerability reduction (e.g., improved access to water, equipment, risk reduction resources, health outreach); structured partnerships, cost-sharing, or co-management agreements for mitigation.</p> <hr/> <p>Collective knowledge-sharing, preparedness, and response outside formal channels; ancestral fire stewardship and intergenerational knowledge transmission (e.g., fire lore, seasonal calendars); cultural burning governed by customary institutions or leadership; fire-use practices tied to social norms, land-use traditions, and biocultural heritage; peer-to-peer awareness through informal networks; observation-based risk signalling; fire stewardship embedded in rural subsistence (e.g., hunting, gathering, agriculture, herding); place-based ecological knowledge applied to fuel management and ecosystem services.</p>
Humanitarian (disaster-oriented)	Crisis-driven mechanisms focused on preparing for, responding to, and recovering from wildfire disasters. This domain typically activates when fires exceed natural variability and overwhelm existing management	Emergency planning and evacuation (routes, shelters, staging areas, signage); crisis communication systems; search and rescue (including cross-jurisdictional coordination); disaster relief and immediate aid (food, water, medical care, shelter);

capacities. Guided by global disaster risk reduction frameworks (e.g., the Sendai Framework), humanitarian governance increasingly extends beyond state-led 'command and control' models to involve complex, multi-actor, and often transboundary responses. Interventions frequently prioritise short-term, externally driven aid, which can overshadow locally grounded, long-term recovery, particularly where structural inequalities amplify risk and exposure.

post-fire recovery (damage assessments, debris clearance, needs-based aid); community resettlement or relocation; psychosocial support; legal and administrative aid (disaster declarations, insurance claims, compensation); fundraising and resource mobilisation (e.g., NGO relief campaigns); protections for vulnerable groups in evacuation, shelter, and recovery; international humanitarian coordination (e.g., UN, Red Cross); "Build Back Better" recovery to reduce future risk and enhance resilience.

Ecological

Governance mechanisms that work with dynamic ecological processes, rather than relying solely on suppression or engineered control, to mitigate wildfire risk and enhance landscape resilience. This domain draws on social-ecological systems thinking to restore ecosystem functions and dynamics (e.g., biodiversity, ecological succession, habitat connectivity) through adaptive, long-term, pyrodiverse management. It prioritises alignment with ecological realities, such as delayed feedbacks and non-linear system responses, rather than short-term political or institutional cycles. Scientific, Indigenous, and local knowledge are integrated to address fuel dynamics, drought, ecosystem degradation, and broader landscape health.

Pyrodiverse fire regime planning (restoring natural variability, ecological memory, species-specific fire adaptations); let-burn policies and managed wildfires; ecosystem health monitoring and restoration (e.g., drought stress, invasive species, habitat recovery, soil stability); rewilding for self-regulating fire-adapted landscapes; biodiversity-informed risk governance (e.g., habitat connectivity, species protection); nature-based mitigation (e.g., greenbelts, wetlands, riparian buffers); adaptive, long-term ecosystem management; fire exclusion zones for sensitive habitats or species; hydrological restoration to support fire-resilient moisture regimes; degradation prevention measures focused on enhancing public health outcomes (e.g., mitigating respiratory problems).
